

A spore suspension was sprayed onto the border row of each plot to provide a source of inoculum. Disease was assessed at the milk stage and 1 wk before harvest. Number of infected panicles, degree of disease severity, and yield were recorded from selected areas in each experimental plot 1 × 2 m².

We found a close relationship between disease incidence and disease severity ($r^2 = 0.93$), and between disease severity and yield ($r^2 = 0.63$). Yield loss was calculated as

$$\frac{(\text{Yield of disease-free plot} - \text{yield of infected plot}) \times 100}{\text{yield of disease-free plot}}$$

When disease severity is high, grain loss increases. We obtained a significant regression function of percent yield loss on disease severity ($y = 4.287 \times -0.146$, $R^2 = 0.623$) (see figure). □

A new weed host for rice yellow dwarf (RYD) pathogen

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We screened 19 weed species for susceptibility to RYD by inoculating 20 plants/species with 5 RYD-viruliferous *Nephotettix virescens* per plant for 24 h.

Only *Echinochloa colona* developed symptoms similar to those caused by the RYD agent on rice. Symptoms appeared 43 d after inoculation (DAI) at the base of some tillers in 40% of the plants. RYD symptoms appeared 28.5 DAI in control rice variety TN1. When shoots of infected weed plants were cut at ground level, all the new growth showed RYD symptoms.

Weed species that did not show symptoms were *Cyperus rotundus*, *C. difformis*, *C. iria*, *Fimbristylis miliacea*, *Ammannia baccifera*, *Brachiaria mutica*, *Chenopodium album*, *Cynodon dactylon*, *Digitaria sanguinalis*, *Digitaria setigera*, *Echinochloa crus-galli*, *E. glabrescens*, *Eleusine indica*, *Ischaemum rugosum*, *Leptochloa chinensis*, *Marsilea quadrifolia*, *Panicum capillare*, and *Portulaca oleracea*.

To test whether *E. colona* can transmit RYD to rice, one infected *E. colona* plant was used as an inoculum source for 50 *N. virescens*. Rice plants were inoculated with five viruliferous leafhoppers each. The RYD agent was

transmitted to 60% of the rice plants. Incubation period in rice was 30.8 d. Tiller numbers increased 224% and height of infected rice plants was 20 cm less than that of healthy rice plants. □

Status of brown spot (BS) and narrow brown leaf spot (NBLs) in eastern Uttar Pradesh (UP), India

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BS caused by *Helminthosporium oryzae* Breda de Haan [*Cochliobolus miyabeanus* (Ito & Kuribayashi) Drechsler ex Dastur] and NBLs caused by *Cercospora oryzae* Miyake [*Sphaerulina oryzae* Hara] commonly occur in wet season (1 Jun-30 Nov) rice. We surveyed BS and NBLs in 5,000 sites in eastern UP, 1977-87. We also conducted 5 trials on their epidemiology and control.

Early-maturing (EM) timely sown (TS) (sown before 20 Jun) varieties escape NBLs and, sometimes, BS too. But in BS, postflowering infections in highly susceptible varieties can reach a

disease score of 6 by the hard dough stage. Two sprays of mancozeb, at 2 kg/1,000 liters water per ha, controlled BS but did not significantly increase yield. Grain discoloration was reduced by more than 50%.

Late sown medium maturity (MM) and TS late maturity (LM) varieties suffer most from BS and give full phenotypic expression to their genetic susceptibility. Infection commonly starts at maximum tillering and is severe (score of 9) by flowering time. In highly fertilized (120 to 150 kg N/ha) fields, 10 to 20% tillers lose normal foliage. Under moderate fertility (100 kg N/ha), yield loss is 10 to 20% in unprotected plots. Two sprays of carbendazim (0.05%) control the disease economically.

In late sown MM and normal sown LM varieties, BS and NBLs cause simultaneous infections, scoring 8 and 9 together (see table). Foliage loss of 5-25% and yield loss of 10-30% are common. Two sprays of mancozeb

Rice lines with high (6 and above) infection scores for BS, NBLs, and mixed BS-NBLs. Faizabad, UP, India, 1980, 1981, and 1986 wet seasons.

Designation	Lines (no.) with disease score ^a		
	BS	NBLs	BS-NBLs
IET7302, RP1579-1585-20-28	6	6	
CR194-523, KD14-1-39	6	7	
IET nos. 8002, 8101, 8540, 8543, 8544, 8845, 8582, 8583, 8642, 9186, 9187, 9188, RP2071-18-1-1	6	8	
CR317-166, CN836-3-8	6	9	
IET5656, RPI796-78-2-1-1-1	8	6	
WGL 47969, RP1579-1615-30-21-36	8	8	
RP1579-28-54	9	9	
IET6658			6
IET nos. 4087, 4155, 5882, 5883, 6144, 6272, Jagannath			8
IET nos. 5882, 5890, 5897, 6212, 6271, 6314, Pankaj			9

^aBy Standard evaluation system for rice (1980).